

D1.2 Data Management Plan

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Abstract

This report constitutes the Data Management Plan. Data types are described and methods for their classification are provided as well as roles and responsibilities for their management, storage, maintenance, etc.. FAIR data principles applications are described together with allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ALCHIMIA project. It includes the description of what kind of data will be collected, exploited, and generated during the project, how they will be managed, stored and published and who will be the responsible.

Such information will include both reference, industrial, design, research, protocols and training data such as datasets and information exchanged during the development, validation and test stages, descriptions and performances data of developed tools, economic, environmental and social impact data and results, original research data, Open Source generated code, scientific publications, white papers, training materials, etc.

Some of the information will be only shared between the consortium while other will be publicly available. The sharing and publishing platforms are among others OwnCloud platform, the project website, social networks, Journal websites, Zenodo and GitHub.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

In ALCHIMIA it is expected the collection, handling, analysis, use, processing and generation of several kind of data and information. For this reason, the present document, constituting the Deliverable 9.3, aims at providing information and guidance on the correct management of ALCHIMIA-related data.

This is the so-called Data Management Plan (DMP) and can be considered as the data "*data sheet and manuals*" allowing knowing the kind of data to be handled, their features and the rules for their interpretation and usage as well as their verification and reuse during and after the project.

For the ALCHIMIA-related data, a description is provided including, besides their typology, their source, the (meta)data used for their explanation, preservation and maintenance, the policies for their storage, access, sharing, protection, exploitation, as well as to make them accessible for their reuse, in accordance with EC's FAIR Data Management principles and guidelines.

This DMP will define also specific roles and the allocation of resources for the management of data.

1.2 Definitions

In this document some terms will be frequently found. Below their definitions according to Oxford Languages is provided:

- **Dataset** - A collection of related sets of information that is composed of separate elements but can be manipulated as a unit.
- **Metadata** - A set of data that describes and gives information about other data.
- **Repository** – A central location in which data is stored and managed.
- **Confidential** - Intended to be kept secret.
- **Open-Access** - The unrestricted right or opportunity to use or benefit from something, in particular academic writing or research.

1.3 Document Structure

After the introduction provided in this section, the following section provides information on the type of data circulating in the ALCHIMIA project, the steps for their classifications the roles and responsibilities related to data management and some brief descriptions of exploited repositories and sharing platforms. Then section 3 introduces FAIR principles and describes how they are applied within ALCHIMIA. section 4 provides a summary of ALCHIMIA data. Finally following sections are finalized to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects. How other research outputs are treated in the project is shortly described in the final section.

2 Data Management Strategy

This chapter provides information on the type of data will be collected, exploited and generated during ALCHIMIA and the related steps for classifying them. Finally, roles and responsibilities are defined.

2.1 Data types and potential users

Different data types will be managed during the project. Data classification depends on their features as well as their origin. In particular, the data types reported in Table 1 are expected to be circulated and managed during ALCHIMIA.

Table 1: Data Types

ID	Type	Description
COD	Code	Tools, Algorithm code
DES	Design	Information about the design of tools, algorithms, and their architecture or for the definition of a scenario and/or a simulation
EXP	Experimental	Data in the forms of numbers collecting results of tools tests as well as of the implementation of ALCHIMIA system.
IMG	Image	Data in the forms of image
IND	Industrial	Data in the forms of numbers coming from industrial partners historical database and/or analyses before the implementation of ALCHIMIA system.
PRO	Protocol	Data including the procedure to be followed for a particular purpose
REF	Reference	Data coming from literature or from other external sources used as reference
SUR	Survey	Data derived from specific survey or interview
TXT	Text	Text database or unstructured data in the form of text

According to the accessibility, data can be furtherly divided in two further categories, as reported in the Table 2.

Table 2: Accessibility data classification

ID	Type	Description
CO	Confidential	Data that cannot be publicly shared for internal regulations, legal and/or competition reasons, business, industrial and/or trade secrets that data providers ought to comply with.
PU	Public	All the data that will be fully published according to Open Science principles.

Together with the differentiation of data types, also final users can be different. Potential users are the following:

- ALCHIMIA consortium (the whole consortium)
- ALCHIMIA models, algorithms, tools developers
- ALCHIMIA Industrial partners
- ALCHIMIA Social scientists
- ALCHIMIA Environmental scientists
- Software developer companies
- Steelmaking and process industry
- Students
- Workers/Workforce
- Scientific Communities

ALCHIMIA partners will have the access to all or part of the confidential data while the other listed users will have the possibility to consult only public data.

All the tables and lists included in this subsection will be updated if new data types or users will emerge during the project evolution.

2.2 Data Management steps

As emerged in the previous subsection, different data types will be collected, used and generated during the project runtime. Therefore, a stepwise approach has been defined through a series of questions to rightly cluster the data and consequently to manage them correctly. The two following flowcharts (Figure 1 and Figure 2) depicts respectively the questions allowing the definition of the different data types and if they are considered confidential or not.

Figure 1 – Data type definition flowchart

Figure 2 – Data accessibility definition flowchart

2.3 Roles and Responsibilities

Right application of this DMP can be possible only through a structured division of roles and responsibilities. Table 3 reports all the designed and involved figures (also supporting ones).

Table 3: Roles and responsibilities for DMP application and support

ID	Role	Responsibilities	Designed partner(s)
PDC	Project data contact (DMP leader)	Reserving DM dedicated time slot at project plenary meetings, prepare and lead related discussions (only if needed)	SSSA with the support of ATOS (as Project Coordinator)
		Informing EC about work done, outcomes, publications and related published data or of the reasons led to the definition of a specific dataset as confidential	
		Hosting and maintaining the OwnCloud platform as internal ALCHIMIA sharepoint and repository	
		Providing a service to be contacted for further questions and work related to DM also after the ALCHIMIA end	
DMP_CR	DMP Coordinators	Developing and implementing DMP	SSSA with the support of ATOS (as Project Coordinator)
		Supervising DMP application	
		Communicating DMP to all the partners	
		Making periodical checks to be sure data are correctly uploaded in repository	
		Ensuring data availability	
DMP_CM	DMP Committee	Guiding partners involved in a specific WP for the application of DMP	WP Leaders (i.e. ATOS, CAR, SSSA, CEL, MI)
		Controlling data quality and consistency	
		Evaluating and approving data considered suitable to be published	

ID	Role	Responsibilities	Designed partner(s)
		Monitoring overall data flow	
DMP_U	DMP Users	Respecting DMP	All the partners
		Collecting, managing, generating, validating, updating and storing datasets and metadata	
		Identifying confidential data or project results suitable for publication	
		Uploading data suitable for publication after eventual modifications required by DMP_CR	
		Making back-up and preserving data	
		Consulting all the other partners involved in specific data generation	
TC	Technical Coordinator (see D.1.1 – Project Handbook)	Supporting the identification of data collected during the project and of related outcomes eventually suitable for publication	BFI
EM	Exploitation Manager (see D.1.1 – Project Handbook)	Supporting in disseminating results in Open Access/publicly	MI
EtM	Ethical Manager (see D.1.1 – Project Handbook)	Monitoring the respect of DMP described ethical aspects	SSSA

2.4 Data Archiving, Sharing, Publishing and Preserving Infrastructure

Within ALCHIMIA, data storing, sharing, publishing and preserving will be done through an infrastructure including internal SharePoint and web-based platforms for allowing long term access to all circulated and generated data and results.

Brief descriptions of main exploited platforms are provided below:

- **ALCHIMIA website** – It provides information on the general ALCHIMIA approach, expected goals and on the consortium. Then a section is dedicated to results and all the open access materials: the guest can download related files or will be transferred to open access repositories or publisher's website (in case of articles). The list of the events and a blog section are also included.
- **OwnCloud** - it constitutes the internal SharePoint for ALCHIMIA data and results. OwnCloud is a suite of client server software for creating and using file hosting services. With respect to other similar software, it is open-source and therefore it can be installed without restrictions. PDC is hosting and maintaining ALCHIMIA OwnCloud platform and the access is ensured to all the consortium partners who can upload, update, and read data and files.
- **Zenodo** – it is an open access repository that was developed for OpenAIRE project, and it is maintained by CERN. It allows researchers to store and share their results in different formats and for all scientific disciplines. It supports both publication of scientific, white papers and structured research data. The uploaded results/data are structured by using metadata that are licensed under CC license. The property rights and/or the ownership of a results is not affected by uploading it in Zenodo. Finally, Zenodo provides a link to GitHub.
- **GitHub** – it is a Git-based Internet hosting service for open-source software projects. It allows for instance the Git distributed revision control, the access control, bug tracking, task management, continuous integration, etc..

3 FAIR Data Principles

This DMP follows the EC FAIR Data Management principles and guidelines; in particular, it complies with the "*The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*" by Wilkinson et. al. [1].

Wilkinson et al. [1] FAIR principles comprise the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of data and "*put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals*". All these principles are linked one to the other and the right following of one of them gives advantages in achieving the others.

Considering the ALCHIMIA-related data, FAIR data principles apply completely to datasets suitable and available for public use; but, although with specific adaptations and rules, they are applied also in case of datasets considered confidential or sensible.

Details on the data management policy following FAIR data principles are provided in the following subsections.

3.1 Findability

Data cannot be used if they cannot be found; therefore, a requirement in data management is to make data finding as easy as possible for both humans and computers, consortium partners and external users.

In this context, the following suggestions were provided by Wilkinson et al. [1]:

- (Meta)Data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- Data are described with rich metadata (see subsection 3.4)
- Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- (Meta)Data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Taking this in mind, this DMP ensures the findability of all the ALCHIMIA-related data both inside the consortium especially for intermediate/sensible/confidential information as well as outside the consortium for open access data and research outputs.

The starting point is a standardized data file naming convention including the following information:

1. Acronym of the project – [ALCHIMIA].
2. Number of the related work package – [WPx]
3. Number of related task – [Tx.y]
4. Number of related deliverable (if any, otherwise "D_na") – [Dx.z]
5. A unique chronological number of the data – [n]
6. Name of data - [DataName]
7. Type of data (see Figure 1) – [TYP]
8. Accessibility of data (see Figure 2) – [ACC]
9. Date - [YYMMDD]
10. Name of who generates the data [Creator]

11. Version number that will be incremental at each revision [vm.p]

The result is the following:

ALCHIMIA_WPx_Tx.y_Dx.z_n_DatasetName_TYP_ACC_YYMMDD_Creator_Vm.p

The data file naming convention makes the files unique and retraceable even if data will not get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) (e.g., sensible or internal data shared between partners).

Depending on the data type, indeed, storage will be ensured both in partners infrastructure/internal consortium archives as well as in public repositories (see subsections 2.4 and 3.2). Only in this case, data will be saved with DOI allowing the facilitation of their identification and achieving effective and persistent citation. On the other side for internally stored data, the data file name will act as "*internal persistent identifier*".

Each dataset's DOI should be used to all the related publications to easily identify the linked datasets. Furthermore, data will be kept published in a data catalogue (e.g. CKAN or AI4EU) that uses standard metadata formats

The metadata describing the ALCHIMIA data will include the information provided in subsection 3.4.

Search keywords common to the ALCHIMIA application field (e.g. Artificial intelligence, Intelligent Systems, Multi Agent Systems, Metallurgy, Green Deal, Federated Learning, Optimisation, Decarbonisation, Trustworthy AI) and describing the dataset or content of the data will be also included in the metadata and will be provided when a dataset is uploaded to a repository aiming at optimising possibilities of finding and re-use (see subsection 3.4)

The expected publication of the project resources in the AI4EU European AI-on-demand platform and the use of keywords will make possible to search datasets easily.

As final remark, cross-referencing between different data must be ensured each time a partner generates a new data.

3.2 Accessibility

The definition of accessibility provided by Wilkinson et al. [1] consists of the following statements:

- (Meta)Data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
- The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Therefore, accessibility directly follows data findability and is fundamental to increase the impact of data and projects results. Accessibility can be achieved through authentication and authorization. The first consists of proving the identity of a user, while authorization concerns the check of the specific access rights or privileges of the authenticated user because not all the users have the possibility to consult a data.

The access to the data (including results) and related sharing will be maximized during ALCHIMIA within and outside the consortium. Although the policy “as open as possible” will be followed and CC-BY-SA licenses will be promoted (see subsection 3.4), some of the data will be considered confidential (see Figure 2).

All the data obtained from public repositories will be offered in the same way as soon as it is available. While in the case of data provided by partners and/or generated during the project, an evaluation will be done and the confidentiality of a data as well as the open access policy will be defined following the rules outlined in the Grant Agreement respectively in Article 13 and Article 17 and in the Consortium Agreement. Further specific rules/steps to decide if a data can be considered public or confidential are provided in subsection 2.1 of this document.

The access to data considered suitable to be public will be provided through:

- Publications in scientific journals ensuring the possibilities of having the Gold Open Access
- Presentation at conferences
- The project website
- Social Networks (i.e. LinkedIn and Twitter)
- Zenodo repository or any other repository complying with the FAIR Data Principles for open access research data
- GitHub repository for tools/algorithm open-source codes

In case of data considered suitable for open access or of data used for developing a paper, not subject to protection/embargo, and in case their release does not jeopardize the project's main objective, the procedure depicted in the flowchart in Figure 3 will be carried out to facilitate their upload in open-access online platforms. During the process, DMP Committee will consider IPR rules as defined in Article 16 of Grant Agreement, in Consortium Agreement and in the related Deliverable D.6.1 to avoid any issues and conflicts.

On the other side, when a data is considered confidential a justification must be provided by the data responsible considering the rules previously cited (see Figure 2). If further reasons will emerge, this DMP will be updated. A confidential data can be subject to anonymization, aggregation, minimization, normalization or sampling procedures that can make them free from sensitive information and thus suitable to be published.

Confidential data access will be ensured in the consortium through:

- OwnCloud if the authorization is provided to all the ALCHIMIA consortium
- Internal partner infrastructure/repositories if the authorization is only for some partners of the consortium

In the case of data surely to be protected, involved partner should notify the project coordinator, all the consortium beneficiaries and the DMP Committee as soon as possible to ensure the optimum level of confidentiality and the use of this data without issues already from an early stage of the project.

Figure 3 – Open-access data uploading steps

3.3 Interoperability

As usual, Wilkinson et al. [1] definition of interoperability considers the following points:

- (Meta)Data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
- (Meta)Data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- (Meta)Data include qualified references to other (meta)data

More generally, interoperability means facilitating the data integration between them.

Consequently, in order to increase the interoperability of data during ALCHIMIA, the following rules will be followed:

- Datasets will be published in standard forms according to the manufacturing and IT domains (e.g CSV, ETSI CIM, AAS or NGS-LD, FIWARE common data models, etc.)
- Further admissible formats for particular type of data will be XLS/XLSX, TXT, PDF, DOC/DOCX, TIFF, JPEG, PNG, JPG, etc.
- Whenever possible SI Units will be used in datasets
- Commonly used vocabularies will be used for the metadata
- Reference to other (meta)data are always provided
- Same wording and acronyms consistent to standard of publications will be used
- OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability will be followed [2]

3.4 Reusability

Wilkinson et al. [1] provided the following definition of the last FAIR principle:

- (Meta)Data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
- (Meta)Data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
- (Meta)Data are associated with detailed provenance
- (Meta)Data meet domain-relevant community standards

Reusability is indeed related to the optimization of the reuse of collected and generated datasets. For reaching the scope, significant efforts will be spent for well-describing in a sufficient clear and exhaustive way all the (meta)data; a general overview of attributes that will be included in ALCHIMIA metadata is provided in Table 4.

The following policy will be followed whenever possible:

- Data collected from other sources will be provided as available originally.
- For those datasets provided from the project and evaluated suitable for public use, licenses like CC BY-SA will be promoted. These kinds of licence allow reusing and adaptation, while still requiring attributing the author; moreover, changing the original license is not allowed.
- Further licence will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

As for accessibility (see subsection 3.2), also reusability will be facilitated by the uploading of the suitable datasets to Zenodo or similar repositories. Furthermore, open accessible datasets will be made available to third parties after they are generated, and the access will be ensured for at least one year (renewable) after the completion of the project for improving the reusability. Possible restrictions (e.g. embargo or restrictions from editors or conference organizers) should be needed to be respected before the sharing of datasets and will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

The responsible of maintaining the data after the end of the project and guiding for their reuse is who generate the data and the PDC.

Table 4: Metadata attributes

Attribute	Description
Persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, if applicable)	Dataset long-lasting reference
Internal standard name	Standardized data file name (see subsection 3.1)
Creator/Responsible Partner	Who created/firstly shared the dataset
Type of data	Type of the data
Description	Brief dataset description
Aim	How data are used
Work Package/Task /Deliverable	Associated work package, task and/or deliverable
Origin	The data source or how data have been generated
Processing	How data have been processed
Repository	Where data will be uploaded
Language	Languages used in the dataset
Acronym List	Explanation of used abbreviations
Format	Data formats
Software	Software needed to create, use, analyse, read data
Expected size	Estimate of dataset size
Keywords / Tags	Keywords describing the data content
Version	Dataset Version
Date of first Repository Submission	Release date (YY MM DD)
Date of last modification	Last modification date (YY MM DD)
Access Information	Confidential or Public
Accessibility	Rights information on the data use
License	Legal agreement between the creator of the data and the end-user
Preview	An example of data

During ALCHIMIA several standards will be followed to allow replicability of tests and carried out work; in addition, a dedicated task (T6.2) is finalized to standardization for creating a favourable environment for successful standardisation and exploitation of results.

Finally, a Data Quality Assurance Process (DQAP) is defined and will be followed to ensure a suitable quality of the data that are generated within all the duration of the project. The indicators that will be considered in the DQAP are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Data Quality Assurance Process Indicators

Indicator	Description
Validity	Data must be suitable, sufficiently accurate and valid for the intended use
Reliability	Data collection and generation methods must remain stable over time
Clarity	Data details must be enough to represent the phenomenon of interest
Integrity	Data must be continuously accurate and consistent
Up-to-dateness	Data must be regularly collected, updated and always available if needed
Completeness	All needed data elements, variables, records, values must be ensured and known

4 Data Summary

The following Table 6 provides a list of data that are expected to be collected, analysed, used and generated within ALCHIMIA. In the table, besides the type, the potential user and the accessibility of data, a series of information is provided concerning the scope of the data, its origin, the responsible partner and the link with previous/other data. In addition, the information provided in the table for each data includes also the possible format(s) and an estimation of the number of stored values as well as of its storage size.

Probably the list provided is not exhaustive, therefore it will be updated within all the ALCHIMIA duration.

Table 6: List of expected ALCHIMIA data

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
Scrap market data	REF, IND	Provide data/info on scrap for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses	Market	CELSA, FdT	ALCHIMIA developer partners and environmental scientists	Excel file, CSV, PDF	Up to 100 files, up to 500 MB	CON	Data from previous projects
Scrap pictures	IMG		Industrial partners	CELSA		TIFF, PNG, JPEG	Up to 5000 images, up to 10 GB storage space		
Scrap inventory and characterization data	IND			CELSA, FdT		Excel, CSV, JSON, API, PDF	Up to 100000 numerical values, up to 100 files, up to 10 GB storage space (considering all the selected data)		
Suppliers' data	REF, IND	Provide data/info on other input materials for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses							
Quality check data	IND	Provide data/info on input materials including scrap for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses							
EAF process data	IND	Provide data on EAF process for modelling/ simulation/	CELSA						

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
		optimization/further analyses							
Steel analysis data	IND	Provide data/info on steel for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses							
Steel grade inventory	IND	Provide data/info on steel for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses							
By-products data	IND	Provide data/info on by-products for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses		FdT					
Intermediated products chemical analyses data	IND	Provide data/info on intermediated and final products for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses							
Thermal analyses data	IND								
Product acoustic emission analyses data	IND								
Product mechanical feature analyses data	IND								
Intermediate product X-ray check analyses	IND, IMG								
Return material data	IND								

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data	
		reason, amount) for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses								
Foundry process data	IND	Provide data on foundry process for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses								
Energy consumption data	IND	Provide data on energy consumption from different sources (e.g. electricity, natural gas) for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses								CELSA, FdT
Emission data	IND	Provide data on emissions (e.g. CO ₂) for modelling/ simulation/ optimization/further analyses								CELSA, FdT
Production plan data	TXT, IND	Provide data on production scheduling for simulation/optimization		CELSA, FdT						
Human factor data	SUR	Provide info to understand organisational and employment implications, emerging skills and training needs due to of novel	Survey, interviews between partners and stakeholder	CAR	ALCHIMIA Consortium and software developer companies, scientific communitiee	Word file, PDF	Up to 10 files, 10-100 MB	PU	Data from end users, previous projects and from technical standards	

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
		digital technologies insertion			dealing with similar topics				and directives
System requirements	DES	Provide design indications for developing the different tools/algorithms included in the ALCHIMIA system	Developers, Industrial and Social Scientists Partners	CEL	ALCHIMIA Consortium	Word file, PDF	Up to 10 files, 10-100 MB	CON	
Design and specification of ALCHIMIA system architecture	DES	Provide all the info on the ALCHIMIA system	Developers Partners	ATOS		Word file, PDF	Up to 10 files, 10-100 MB		
Federated learning infrastructure framework architecture and code	DES, CODE	Implement Federated Learning	Developers partners	ATOS	ALCHIMIA Consortium and steelmaking and process industry, software developer companies, scientific community dealing with similar topics	Matlab, Python files	Up to 100 files, up to 2 GB	PU after dedicated data/info transformation processes	Data from previous projects, from internal development and from technical standards and directives
Protection algorithm code	CODE	Avoid data and model poisoning attacks							
Confidentiality methodologies	CODE	Maintain data confidentiality							
Continual learning methodologies and code	CODE	Implement Continual Learning							
Services code for Transfer learning and	CODE	Ensure that the resulting models produced by FL generalize properly for							

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
Domain adaptation		new industries and use-cases.		EXUS					
Pre-processing data code	CODE	Allow data analyses and preparation							
Communication protocols	PRO, CODE	Allow data fluxes and communication between ALCHIMIA tools							
Knowledge generated after data analysis	EXP	Provide found relations between data		EXUS, BFI, SSSA	ALCHIMIA developers, Industrial partners	Excel, Word files, PDF	Up to 10 files, up to 100 MB	CON or PU after dedicated data/info transformation processes	Data from previous projects
Models code, features and results	COD, EXP, TXT	Implement models for prediction of plant and product behaviour, allow their use and evaluate related results		BFI, SSSA	ALCHIMIA Industrial partners	Matlab, Python files, Word, Excel files, PDF	Up to 50 files, up to 1 GB	CON	Data from previous projects
LCA framework code, procedure, and results	CODE, EXP, TXT	Implement LCA for impact assessment as support/part of optimizer, allow its use and evaluate related results	LCA experts, industrial partners	SSSA	ALCHIMIA Consortium and steelmaking and process industry, software developer companies, scientific community dealing with similar topics	Excel, Word files, PDF	Up to 100 files, up to 200 MB	CON or PU after dedicated data/info transformation processes	Data from libraries
Optimization framework code, features and results	CODE, EXP, TXT	Implement optimizer for finding "magic recipe" to decrease emissions, energy consumption and to improve product quality, allow its use	Developers partners			Matlab, Python files, Word, Excel files, PDF	Up to 50 files, up to 1 GB		Data from end users projects

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
		and evaluate related results							
Scenario specification data	DES	Design scenarios	Developers and industrial partners	CEL, FdT	ALCHIMIA Consortium and steelmaking and process industry, software developer companies, scientific community dealing with similar topics, Workers, Students	Word file, PDF	Up to 10 files, up to 100 MB	CON	Data from end users
Scenarios and tests results	EXP	Provide results of scenarios and tests after ALCHIMIA system implementation				Excel, Word files, PDF	Up to 50 files, up to 500 MB	PU after dedicated data/info transformation processes	Data from end users, previous projects and from libraries
Techno-economic assessment data	EXP	Provide results of techno-economic analysis as part of the assessment of tool performance after ALCHIMIA system implementation		Excel, Word files, PDF		Up to 10 files, up to 100 MB			
Green Deal contribution data	EXP, TXT	Provide info on ALCHIMIA contribution to Green Deal		SSSA		Word file, PDF	Up to 3 files, up to 50 MB	PU	Data from EC
Environmental impact assessment data	EXP	Provide results of environmental impact assessment after ALCHIMIA system implementation	ALCHIMIA Consortium	MI	Excel, Word files, PDF	Up to 10 files, up to 100 MB	PU after dedicated data/info transformation processes	Data from end users, previous projects and from libraries	
Business and exploitation plan data	PRO	Provide guidance for exploitation and business creation			Word files, PDF	Up to 3 files, up to 50 MB	PU	Data from end users	
Education and Training material	PRO	Provide courses for training and improving skills	Academia and industrial partners	CAR	Word files, PDF, videos	Up to 20 files, up to 5 GB	PU	Data from previous courses	

Name	Type	Aim	Origin	Responsible Partner(s)	Potential User(s)	Potential Format	Estimate Size	Accessibility	Link with previous/ other data
Literature data	REF	Provide reference data for all the different activities to be developed in ALCHIMIA	Literature	The partners who found it	ALCHIMIA Consortium	PDF	N.A.	PU	

5 Allocation of resources

Cost for respecting this DMP, making data FAIR and for their preparation and check are generally personnel costs. Then further costs can be related to storage, backup, preservation, maintenance, sharing, for providing the open-access to research data and publications and for ensuring security. All these costs have been included in projects costs and are eligible for reimbursement, still considering that retroactivity claims are not possible.

Although the aim of the consortium is to preserve the data for a sufficient time period, the costs for long-term preservation of data after the end of the project are difficult to be estimated at this stage, as they depend on the final amount of data collected and generated, and are strictly related to the services offered by repositories (e.g. Zenodo offer free of charge uploading of maximum 50 GB files).

Data Management is planned in WP1 and to be carried out by all the partners in all the WPs under the guidance of DMP Committee and the supervision of DMP Coordinators (see subsection 2.3). In particular, DMP Coordinators, as responsible for DMP implementation have dedicated person-months in WP1 for the development and implementation of this DMP, data access plans, right management and required documentations for main repositories. In addition, they communicate DMP to all the partners. On their side, ALCHIMIA partners are responsible for DMP implementation within the WPs where they are involved, and for all the data they collect, process and generate.

To ensure DMP is continuously respected, if needed, a dedicated time slot would be reserved at the project plenary meetings. Updates will be provided about DMP application on data collected, exploited and generated with particular attention on the reasons drove to the definition of a specific dataset confidential or suitable for public dissemination.

Project coordinator (i.e. ATOS) is hosting the OwnCloud cloud-based exchange platform for all ALCHIMIA partners to allow the sharing and the alignment of communication, reporting documents and data between the consortium.

6 Data Security

Data security will be granted through different actions.

First, multiple copies of all the documents and dataset circulated during the project will be stored in different repositories to avoid data losses:

- In local private repositories of the responsible partner, without public access
- in a duplicated backup hardisk
- In the project OwnCloud in case data is accessible to all the Consortium (Owncloud itself offers real data security and privacy, and ATOS Information Security Policy based on ISO27002 is also applied as reported in D.1.1 – Project Handbook)
- In Zenodo or similar repositories in case of data suitable to be public

In addition, resident backup servers will be used to store documents and datasets for at least one year later ALCHIMIA conclusion.

If possible, confidential and sensitive data/information will be anonymized before sharing to preserve the anonymity of the user/plant generating the data. However, generally, confidential data and information will be circulated through encrypted files (with password) only among partners responsible of the specific activity involving the handling of these data.

Finally, GDPR compliant procedures for data recovery, secure storage and transfer will be applied.

7 Ethical Aspects

Within ALCHIMIA, all partners are devoted to the addressing of all the activities in compliance with ethical principles, the applicable international and national law, and the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement.

As the human-centric philosophy will guide the design of the ALCHIMIA system, the highest level of trust, safety and seamless collaboration between workers and AI-based industrial solutions must be guaranteed. For this reason, the Ethics Guidelines for trustworthy AI proposed by the High-level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG) and the requirements introduced by the Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and the council, laying down harmonised rules on AI (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts will be considered as the core references.

Ethical issues will be addressed both for activity development and for data management and sharing.

Considering that within ALCHIMIA the analysis of "*human factor*" of novel digital technologies insertion (to understand organisational and employment implications, emerging skills and training needs) includes, among others, interviews and surveys, the collection and use of related data will be done with the respect for people, human dignity, protection of the values, rights and interests of the research participants. First, all the human subjects will be involved in voluntary basis and will be adequately informed through informed consent forms that will be available in different languages with terms intelligible to the participants and will be controlled by the EthM, stored by the partner organizing interviews/surveys and by the PDC and managed as confidential data. Only adult participants will be accepted, and no vulnerable individuals, patients or children will be involved. Then anonymization practices will be always carried out to protect privacy and personal data. Also, in case of images/videos will be collected during the project, before their sharing, detected humans will be blurred to avoid identification if no direct consensus is expressed by involved people.

8 Other research outputs

This DMP rules also all the other research outputs not directly mentioned that may be generated or reused throughout ALCHIMIA project. Among these outputs there are software, specific algorithms, graphical user interfaces, workflows, deliverables, reports, etc..

References

- [1]. Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., Bonino da Silva Santos, L., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A. J. G., Growth, P., Grethe, J. S., Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.
- [2]. OpenAIRE Guideline, accessible at <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

Appendix A List of available open access data

An exemplary template to collect information related to data to be stored in open-access repositories is reported in the Table 7. Possible modifications will be evaluated if necessary.

Table 7: Exemplary template to collect information of Open access data

Internal Standard Name	Short Description	Persistent identified	ZENODO (or other open access repository) link	Archiving date	Reusable by third parties	Reuse time

Appendix B Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI HLEG	High-level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
CC	Creative Common
CC-BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike
CODE	Code
DES	Design
DM	Data Management
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP_CM	DMP Committee
DMP_CR	DMP Coordinators
DMP_U	DMP Users
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DQAP	Data Quality Assurance Process
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EthM	Ethical Manager
EXP	Experimental
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IMG	Image
IND	Industrial
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PDC	Project Data Contact
PRO	Protocol
REF	Reference
SUR	Survey

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
TC	Technical Coordinator
TXT	Text
WP	Work Package